

AI Blueprint Factory

Final Report

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The SGX3 Blueprint Factories are intended to help SGX3 better understand the cyberinfrastructure (CI) needs of entire research communities and national-scale cyberinfrastructure providers. Each Blueprint Factory brings together CI professionals, domain scientists, and major infrastructure operators to discuss current challenges and design solutions.

For more information on the SGX3 Blueprint Factories, please visit <https://sciencegateways.org/our-services/blueprint-factories>.

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Executive Summary

Advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), including generative systems like ChatGPT and DeepSeek, are motivating a revolution in academic research computing. Academic researchers are turning to AI to make fundamental strides in their research, creating and providing new models and algorithms, AI-ready datasets, AI-relevant cyberinfrastructure, and more. However, the academic sphere lags behind the private sector in AI resource availability and adoption. Science gateways have long facilitated academic research by simplifying the access and use of advanced computing resources, and promoting collaboration. Can science gateways help academic research communities by promoting access to advanced AI resources, new algorithms and models, and AI-ready datasets?

The NSF Center of Excellence for Science Gateways (SGX3) founded an initiative called the AI Blueprint Factory to address this question. The purpose of the AI Blueprint Factory is to ascertain the AI needs of research communities that use national-scale computing infrastructure, and to make 5 to 10 year forecasts of needed features and resources. Its study team interviewed researchers across disciplines and seniority levels to determine perceived needs, opportunities, and gaps in AI research support. The focus is on fostering the utilization of AI techniques in domain science research, identifying technical capabilities required to support evolving scientific and computing needs, and considering how science gateways can help. In this report, we present our findings from a focus group and 30 interviews with cyberinfrastructure (CI) experts and domain researchers who use AI techniques and methods in their work.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The Artificial Intelligence (AI) Blueprint Factory is a research study by the SGX3 Center of Excellence, an NSF-funded organization whose mission is to “extend access, expand the community, and exemplify good practices for CI through science gateways.”¹ Since 2016, SGX3 and its precursor, the Science Gateways Community Institute (SGCI), has worked with hundreds of science gateways to facilitate

integration with computing and data resources, and address audience, design, funding challenges, and other details of running these collaborative platforms.

Science gateways provide web-based portals to computing, data, and collaborative resources for scientists. Many gateways are beginning to encompass resources that can provide AI functionality and features for research. In this report, we explore the primary challenges facing researchers who use AI features in their work. Furthermore, we consider how gateways and other platforms can better deliver support for AI features, and smooth the entry into AI-assisted research for new adopters.

METHODS

The findings presented in this report are the result of interviews with 30 scientific domain researchers and cyberinfrastructure experts who develop, support, and use AI techniques and methods in the pursuit of their work. These individual interviews provided a wealth of current researcher perspectives on AI-enabled scientific research, originating in a range of scientific domains, seniorities, and research problems. Prior to the interview phase, a focus group held at Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2023 (PEARC'23) established a baseline understanding of the challenges and opportunities for AI use in research computing. A core team of domain researchers and CI experts versed in the use of AI in research prepared the interview questions, recruited interview subjects, directed the inquiry, and conducted the discussions. The leader of the core team took major points and observations from this combination of focus group and interviews to draft this report.

TOPICS COVERED

The report findings section is structured into four subsections, each dedicated to a challenge facing AI-enabled research in scientific and engineering domains. Each begins with a summary of the challenge, identifies capabilities needed to counter the challenge, proposes approaches that can be used to address the challenge, and closes with questions and issues for further consideration and recommendations for future actions.

The four key concerns raised in the report and the proposed approaches to solving them are:

- Access to advanced computing infrastructure
 - ◇ Approach: Engage human capital
 - ◇ Approach: Collaborate with industry
 - ◇ Approach: Prioritize academic work
 - ◇ Approach: Document failures
- Data management and reproducibility
 - ◇ Approach: Data availability and sharing
 - ◇ Approach: Ensuring metadata and provenance
 - ◇ Approach: Data integrity and privacy
- Democratizing AI access for domain science
 - ◇ Approach: AI Facilitators
 - ◇ Approach: Discoverability and accessibility of computing resources
 - ◇ Approach: Science Gateways
 - ◇ Approach: Targeted use cases and examples
- Fostering responsible use of AI in research
 - ◇ Approach: Guidelines and tools for reproducibility
 - ◇ Approach: Interdisciplinary teams
 - ◇ Approach: Education and training
 - ◇ Approach: Human in the loop
 - ◇ Approach: Optimize for efficiency

RECOMMENDATIONS

The report provides recommendations for addressing the key concerns. These recommendations are:

- Recognize the role of Research Software Engineers in building the AI research ecosystem
- Encourage development of data pipelines, tools, and techniques for AI research
- Strengthen standards and guidelines for appropriate AI use in research
- Support and grow science gateways for AI
- Expand teaching of AI
- Forge partnerships between industry and academia
- Identify indicators of success

CONCLUSION

Though AI is increasingly prevalent in contemporary research, its use across the scientific disciplines is still in its early stages. Therefore, the full implications of AI on research, science gateways, and academic computing remain unclear. The AI Blueprint Factory is intended to help determine current research usage of AI techniques and methods, evaluate contemporary pain points, concerns, and issues, and project researcher practices and needs into the future.

This report explores and surveys the challenges that academic researchers face when pursuing their AI-based research in the domain sciences. It is our hope that these findings are useful to a variety of stakeholders, including funders, principal investigators, research computing professionals, domain researchers, AI researchers, cyberinfrastructure experts, and computing infrastructure operators. Cultivating the growth and vigor of academic AI research use will ultimately require sustained efforts at a national scale, and even beyond. Together, academic disciplines, institutions, and funders must coordinate and collaborate if they are to achieve this aim.

Introduction

Science gateways are web platforms or portals, often tailored to specific disciplines, that simplify the complexities of using research computing infrastructure, allowing scientists and educators to focus on research and teaching rather than the installation and compilation of complex software. Here, we consider a science gateway to be any research-focused digital initiative intended for “widely sharing cyberinfrastructure, tools, data, or content, in the service of facilitating knowledge creation.”² Science gateways are designed to facilitate access to datasets, software, computing resources such as supercomputers or cloud services, collaborative features, and specialized scientific equipment ranging from telescopes and particle colliders to environmental sensors. Science gateways have seen significant adoption and influence in domains including neurology, phylogenetics, nanotechnology, and natural disasters. Prominent examples of science gateways include nanoHUB³, DesignSafe⁴, and OpenTopography⁵.

AI-enabled research is triggering a proliferation of science gateways that aim to offer researchers and educators access to AI-ready models, datasets, managed Large Language Models (LLMs), and access to compute resources.⁶⁻¹⁰ Even commercial AI platforms such as HuggingFace are arguably science gateways, delivering access to models, compute cycles, and data, sometimes at a cost to users.¹¹⁻¹³ Science gateways can provide user-friendly environments that combine research computing and AI, helping to drive innovation and bring new communities to AI.

SGX3 and its precursor, the Science Gateways Community Institute (SGCI), has supported science gateway owners, developers, and users since 2016.¹⁴ These NSF-funded projects help advance and support academic science gateways by providing services that include consultation, internships, workforce development programs, an annual conference, and the Blueprint Factories. The Blueprint Factory on Sustainability has recently concluded, resulting in a published report; a study of Materials Science is in preparation now.^{2,15} These Blueprint Factory studies help identify current and future community needs for support, tools, and features for science gateways and other virtual research environments.

Background

Science Gateways and AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been influencing science and industry since the 1950s.¹⁶ From that time until the 1970s, researchers worked to model cognitive processes and teach computers to recognize patterns using artificial neural networks, then in the 1980s, to code and use expert systems. By 2011, the speed of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) increased to the point of exercising a significant advantage over Central Processing Units (CPUs) for running deep learning algorithms.¹⁷ Recent excitement around AI arises in part from a proliferation of large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, Claude AI, and DeepSeek, which have gained attention due to their public user interfaces, ease of use, and ready availability.^{18,19} AI methods show promise for finding novel solutions in research computing and reshaping many aspects of the field. Meanwhile, over two decades, science gateways have become part of the research computing landscape.²⁰ Gateways streamline access to computational solutions, enable users to share simulations and data, and help foster reproducible research.

With this study, the NSF Center of Excellence for Science Gateways (SGX3) is investigating how the community pursuing AI-driven research can benefit from science gateways, and in turn, the science gateways community can benefit from AI techniques in research computing.¹ This study and the other SGX3 Blueprint Factories are intensive endeavors spanning approximately 18 months, focused on ascertaining the technical capabilities necessary for science gateways to support the evolving requirements of scientific domains and computing resources.²¹ The Sustainability Blueprint Factory report was released in 2025; the Materials Science Blueprint Factory is in progress now. Studies on topics such as Quantum Computing and the NSF ACCESS program are planned for the near future.

Motivation

Science gateways have been a boon for research computing, streamlining computational environments for users who need easy access to high-performance computing (HPC), large datasets, or complex software for their work. Ideally, science gateways and other modern research computing infrastructure can be adapted to fit AI-based research practices. However, the needs of AI workflows typically differ from those of typical HPC computations that are so common in research computing.

Figure 1 shows a high-level example of the steps required to prepare, train, evaluate, and deploy a single version of an AI model in research. In the figure, the Data Wrangling box vastly simplifies numerous data management steps, including data cleansing, normalization, metadata capture, versioning, iteration, and so forth. Selecting, adapting, and training the AI model, and the evaluation of the results, are captured in successive boxes, which similarly compress numerous steps. The final box represents the deployment of the AI model for use in inference.

Figure 1: High-level example AI workflow summarizes the stages of preparing, training, and deploying an AI model for research purposes. First the researcher must prepare the data, then train the model, evaluate the results, and finally deploy the model for inference use.

The differences between research HPC and AI workloads like the one diagrammed in Figure 1 can be significant. In both types of computations, researchers must determine the appropriate computing resources, then apply for time on them. For AI workloads in particular, long waits may be necessary to access specialized computing resources appropriate for the work. Furthermore, AI model training can be especially laborious and require considerable time. The AI model training tasks that follow are iterative and interactive, with natural checkpoints, and require different model validation processes than typical HPC workloads.

Moreover, data management is a pivotal concern for AI workloads. Training AI models often requires extensive datasets whose size makes transferring them to needed compute resources a challenge. AI

models are frequently used for data recall and are ideally located near the data source. Models may be updated frequently with incremental training, necessitating careful management of data provenance, which entails tracking and characterizing both the data used to train specific model versions and the model versions used. The subsequent reporting of scientific findings must then specify these myriad details.

Ethical considerations also accompany the proliferation of AI in scientific research. The handling and analysis of the vast amounts of data needed raise concerns about data security, privacy, and the potential for bias in AI models. Researchers and institutions must navigate these challenges responsibly, ensuring that data is used in ways that respect individual privacy and content ownership. Furthermore, researchers must take care that AI models are trained and deployed within the context for which they were intended, and without reinforcing unintentional biases. Only if these considerations are observed can a claim on reproducible science be made.

Taken together, data privacy, resource availability, model suitability, and the orchestration of training, validation, data management, and recall in AI research can be complex. The AI Blueprint Factory explores how researchers across disciplines are using AI, what challenges they face, and how cyberinfrastructure such as science gateways might help address those challenges. The focus of the study is on enabling domain scientists to more effectively apply AI methods in their work, rather than on advancing core AI research itself. Furthermore, the study considers how science gateways and other CI can broaden access to AI techniques, thus enabling domain researchers new to AI to learn about and adopt these approaches.

Methodology

The Blueprint Factory concept is part of an SGX3 objective to envision the future of research computing. A Blueprint Factory study collects data from focus groups and researcher interviews to identify emerging needs and develop a forward-looking blueprint of technical capabilities for science gateways and research computing infrastructure. Each Blueprint Factory study spans approximately 18 months and is guided by a core team consisting of cyberinfrastructure (CI) professionals and science domain experts.²¹ SGX3 aims to conduct additional Blueprint Factories to explore topics that include CI sustainability, materials science, and quantum computing.

The AI Blueprint Factory study used data collected in an early focus group held at the Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2023 conference (PEARC'23), followed by 30 researcher interviews planned and conducted by the Blueprint Factory core team. This section describes the study methodology, including conducting the focus group, selecting the study core team and the interview candidates, drafting interview questions, and conducting and analyzing interviews.

Initial focus group

At the beginning of the study, SGX3 invited members of the research computing community to a focus group to discuss AI and science gateway use in scientific research. The resulting Birds of a Feather (BoF) session, held at Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2023 (PEARC'23), followed a guided format in which focus group participants generated and then ranked ideas based on four questions:

1. What novel modes of computing does AI introduce? Which of these will have the greatest impact on cyberinfrastructure for gateways and national compute resources?
2. How do AI's compute loads and modes affect how data can be shared, moved, and accessed?
3. What are appropriate goals for broadening access to AI-appropriate compute resources?
4. How can AI be used to improve a science gateway?

The discussion highlighted opportunities and concerns related to integrating AI into science gateways. Importantly, participants' remarks encompassed both opportunities to use AI to improve gateways and research computing, and more general opportunities to streamline the use of AI in research. A wide-ranging list of issues, concerns, and opportunities was compiled by focus group participants. Taking the most frequent mentions of ideas, these included:

1. *Providing gateway users with interactive assistance*, including chatbots, guided workflow composition, and guided selection of compute resources;
2. *Enhancing gateway usability*, including caching previous computations, user support, and natural language translation;
3. *Addressing compute and training bottlenecks*, by providing guided model training, interactive computing, and prediction of simulation results; and
4. *Weighing concerns about data access and handling*, including data ethics, data provenance, protected information, and access to training data.

Conclusions derived from the analysis of the session were presented at Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing 2024 (PEARC'24).^{22,23} These conclusions helped SGX3 establish a baseline understanding of concerns, challenges, and goals with respect to AI use in research computing. This understanding was used to inform the interview portion of the AI Blueprint Factory study.

Refer to the Appendices for a description of the group discussion technique used during this focus group.

Selecting the core team and interview candidates

A core team consisting of 3 domain experts and 5 cyberinfrastructure (CI) experts convened to direct the AI Blueprint Factory. The researchers invited to participate have considerable expertise with AI in research; they either use AI in scientific research, or build and support CI for scientific research.

The AI Blueprint Factory core team met to discuss their AI work and prominent questions about AI use in research. Using these discussions as a starting point, they compiled a list of interview candidates from a variety of scientific disciplines, seniority levels, and institutions. All interview candidates considered by the team use advanced AI techniques and methods to address substantive research questions.

Refer to the Participants section for additional information about the interviewees and specific examples of their research problems.

Framing the questions

The team drafted an interview guide based on discussions and on central ideas that surfaced in the Science Gateways AI discussion held at PEARC'23.^{22,23} The guide was designed to encourage free-form discussion during interviews. A recruitment letter and a study information sheet were prepared to help enlist participants.

Refer to the Appendices for the interview guide, participant recruitment letter, and study information sheet.

Conducting interviews

The AI Blueprint Factory core team conducted a total of 30 individual interviews lasting 30 to 90 minutes each. This number of interviews is considered sufficient for qualitative data collection in a study of this type.²⁴⁻²⁷ Core team members who conducted interviews first secured Institutional Review Board (IRB) Exempt approval from their home institutions. Five members of the core team

conducted all interviews, structuring each discussion using the interview guide they developed. The team performed the interviews virtually using Zoom conferencing software to record and automatically transcribe each interview session.²⁸

In the interviews, each researcher was asked about their research domain, current projects, the types of AI they use, their computing resources and data sources, their AI workflow and data management practices, their favored user interfaces for AI access, and concerns about AI, such as resource availability, cost, and ethics.

Analysis and reporting

Text transcripts of the interviews were reviewed for accuracy by the core team, and then analyzed using a variety of methods. In accordance with the IRB approval secured for this study, each individual transcript was coded to mask interviewee identity. A script was used to purge interviewer and interviewee names from the transcripts and code the transcripts with sequential numbers in place of the participants' names. The full-length, coded transcripts were enhanced with additional context about researcher background, specialty, and projects, and then summarized using managed LLMs. Interview summaries ranged from 3-5 pages in length. These summaries helped the core team members to quickly grasp the content of each interview.

The resulting interview summaries were reviewed and compared with full interview transcripts. Following this step, the summaries were provided as input to managed LLMs, which could be repeatedly queried to help characterize the contents, draw out themes, and make observations across the dataset. The core team used Google's NotebookLM, running Gemini model 2.5, for its document capacity, reliability, uptime, document citation feature, and ease of use.²⁹ For validation, conclusions arising from use of the LLM were checked against compiled interview summaries as well as the full interview transcripts in order to combat any tendency for hallucination on the part of the LLM. The full transcripts were consulted regularly so that the interview context was preserved. In the Findings section, interview participants are cited with their coded sequential number when they are quoted directly or when their statements or ideas are paraphrased.

Early results were presented in a talk at the annual SGX3 Science Gateways 2025 conference.³⁰ Study conclusions will be presented in a talk at Practice and Experience in Research Computing 2026 (PEARC'26).

Participants

This section provides a picture of the researchers interviewed for this study, and the work they do in AI. The 30 researchers and experts interviewed for the AI Blueprint Factory conduct research across a number of disciplines, and with widely varying goals. The research tasks these researchers perform using AI include building models of complex biological systems; developing deep learning models for cancer risk prediction and prognosis; testing the security and robustness of published deep learning models; studying how regions of the brain communicate; or working on optimization algorithms for NP-hard problems. Meanwhile, the CI experts that participated in interviews for the AI Blueprint Factory are engaged in varied research whose conclusions will help support domain scientists, such as designing ML algorithms to scale up scientific applications; building cyberinfrastructure to support scientific workflows; or exploring dynamic adaptation for resource computing allocations.

Participant demographics

The 30 researchers who participated in the AI Blueprint Factory interviews represent a diversity of seniorities, research disciplines, and US regions. Interviewees included 4 graduate students, and 9 early career, 10 mid-career, and 7 senior researchers. Here we take early career to mean that fewer than 10 years have elapsed since the researcher's Ph.D. or terminal degree; mid-career to mean that 11 to 20 years have elapsed, and senior to mean that more than 20 years have elapsed since the researcher's Ph.D. Refer to Table 1 for a summary of interviewee demographics.

Participants represented various research disciplines, with 30% of interviewees from Computer Science, 20% from the Physical Sciences, 16.7% from each of Medicine and Engineering, 10% from the Social Sciences, and 6.7% from the Biological Sciences. R1 institutions were best represented, with 80

percent of interviewees affiliated with these institutions with the highest degree of research focus. By region, the majority of researchers interviewed (73%) are located at institutions in the Midwestern and Western regions of the US.

Research Discipline	Count	Region	Count
Computer Science	9	Eastern US	3
Physical Sciences	6	Midwest US	10
Medicine	5	Western US	12
Engineering	5	Southern US	2
Social Sciences	3	Other	3
Biological Sciences	2		

Seniority	Count	Institutional Classification	Count
Graduate Student	4	R1	24
Early Career	9	R2	2
Mid Career	10	Other	4
Senior	7		

Table 1: Demographics of AI Blueprint Factory Interviewees. In total, 30 researchers were interviewed. Counts of researchers by discipline, seniority, institutional classification, and region are shown.

Fully 30% of the interviewees for this study are active in computer science research and cyberinfrastructure development. The inclusion of these computer scientists and cyberinfrastructure (CI) experts is deliberate. The work of these computing experts is critical for exploring and addressing technological and resource questions around AI use, thus providing the necessary background that enables domain scientists to conduct their own AI-enabled research. AI enabled research would not be possible without them and their essential work.

Survey of participants' AI research

Figure 2: AI Blueprint Factory interviewees' AI research tasks. In total, 30 researchers were interviewed. Each researcher's most recent or most prominent AI research project is considered. This simplification enables a mapping of each researcher's work to a single task type.

This section further describes the domain researchers and CI experts who sat for interviews for this study, by exploring the types of research tasks they undertake using AI techniques and methods. Here, each researcher is classified by their most recent or most prominent AI research project. This simplification compresses the view of participating researchers, but makes it possible to map each researcher's work to a single AI type. Refer to Figure 2 for a graphical representation of the research task types that participants use AI to solve, model, or simulate.

The AI task types used by the interviewees are:

1. Scientific Emulation
2. Predictive Modeling
3. Scientific Discovery
4. Knowledge Retrieval
5. Computational Infrastructure

The *Scientific Emulation* category uses AI models to replace computationally expensive solvers and simulations. Five participating researchers perform work in this category. These researchers use generative AI to speed up particle physics simulations to handle immense increases in data volume from detector upgrades; or design neural network frameworks to replace the nuclear solver in stellar evolution codes; or use AI to create surrogate models to perform spatial integration, improving the efficiency of Earth system models; or use machine learning to approximate expensive electronic structure calculations.

The *Predictive Modeling* category includes researchers that develop and use AI models to produce probabilistic predictions of risk, forecast outcomes, or perform classification. Six participating researchers work in this category. These researchers develop deep learning models for early cancer detection and risk prediction; create cancer patient digital twins for real-time prognosis; optimize existing models for disease risk prediction in chronic disease management; or use machine learning on electronic medical records and social media data to predict patient disease risk.

The researchers in the *Scientific Discovery* category use AI models to create new scientific artifacts, optimize designs for scientific instruments or new materials, or discover fundamental laws. Six participating researchers perform work in this category. They use genetic algorithms for instrument design, or to generate new materials; use active learning to accelerate discovery processes for new metallic alloys and materials; perform algorithm development for model discovery, aiming to derive partial differential equations from large datasets; or use graph neural networks to guide the design of new energy materials.

The *Knowledge Retrieval* category consists of participating researchers who leverage LLMs and Natural Language Processing (NLP) for data querying and summarization, or design conversational systems for human interaction. Three participating researchers occupy this category. They fine-tune existing open-source generative AI models and LLMs using domain-specific datasets; design custom AI tools to mitigate misinformation; or operationalize LLMs for use by academic communities.

The *Computational Infrastructure* category includes researchers who support cyberinfrastructure for AI. Ten participating researchers occupy this category. These researchers design distributed systems for LLM workloads; develop algorithms for sparsity and model compression; study metadata that can enable algorithm portability; develop tools and models to boost efficient utilization of HPC resources; and build cyberinfrastructure to support construction of AI workflows. These researchers also work on governance and safety, using AI models to test other models for security, robustness, FAIRness,

and compliance; developing “technology metadata” to govern AI tool adoption; and studying AI reproducibility.

Participants in the AI Blueprint Factory study represent a diversity of science and engineering disciplines, seniorities, and institutions. Overall, the research they pursue is heavily focused on using AI to optimize scientific calculations and processes; to discover new techniques, materials, and sensors; and to study, safeguard, and improve AI use in research.

Findings: Challenges and Promising Approaches

This section explores the challenges and capabilities of providing an AI ecosystem that can effectively meet the needs of academic domain research over the next 5 to 10 years. It then summarizes approaches that could aid in addressing these challenges.

The two most substantial challenges to AI use in academic domain science research are competition for access to advanced computing infrastructure and the problem of democratizing AI access. These two concerns occupy either end of the experience spectrum for AI researchers, as one is the province of experienced researchers who need access to advanced computing infrastructure, and the other relates to those who are just beginning to engage in AI related research. Nonetheless, they are the predominant issues to confront in order to strengthen the use of AI in academic research. Other concerns cited by researchers are also important: data issues for AI, including security, metadata, and privacy; and means for fostering appropriate AI use in research.

Challenge: Access to advanced computing infrastructure

Competition for the specialized compute systems needed for AI use in research is one of the leading issues mentioned by interviewees in the AI Blueprint Factory study. The academic computing systems suitable for the largest AI workloads are supported by the US Department of Energy (DOE), the NSF ACCESS program, and the NSF National AI Research Resource (NAIRR) Pilot program and feature the most powerful cyberinfrastructure available to the public sector.^{31,32} Researchers interviewed for this study indicated that they commonly use a combination of these computing resources to run their largest AI workloads.

US investment in AI resources is at record levels. In the first 9 months of 2025, AI startups in the US raised \$160 billion to fuel their compute needs.³³ Though academia is also investing in hardware to run AI, academic computing systems are typically smaller than those maintained by industry leaders in AI, often by “10 or even 100 times” and are frequently oversubscribed.³⁴ As a result, academic researchers who pursue resource-intensive areas of AI, such as computer vision and generative AI, must compete with one another for access to these scarce resources.³⁵ This forces such researchers to compromise their work, either by scaling calculations down or shifting priorities to smaller problems. While commercial cloud platforms offer scalability for computing and may appear to provide a solution, their use is typically billed per hour, making them too expensive for sustained research use.³⁶ Moreover, cloud resources may not offer sufficient memory, fast interconnect, or other features needed for the most advanced AI research tasks.³⁷ In the face of this shortfall, academic demand for access to AI-capable compute resources is only growing.

Encouraging domain scientists to pursue research that is impartial and not driven by commercial interests can result in innovations and new discoveries unrelated to monetary gain or stock prices. But, as one researcher stated, academia is being relegated to “small AI”, whereas industry, with its massive computational resources, pursues “big AI”.³⁷ Though scarcity can drive the development of more efficient computational solutions, the resources currently available to researchers are often insufficient for the calculations they need to run and the datasets they need to accommodate.³⁶ Overall, the most capable academic systems are badly oversubscribed; and, in general, existing academic systems are far behind those hosted by industry and are inadequate to meet the burgeoning demand for AI-enabled research in the domain sciences.³⁵⁻³⁹

Capabilities needed

- Computing hardware infrastructure with sufficient capacity (including memory, GPUs, and other accelerators) to accommodate training of frontier models, fine-tuning models, and running model inference. This would prevent researchers from experiencing significant bottlenecks and impediments to performing AI research or research that uses AI.
- Software that can effectively and efficiently leverage available hardware. Software frameworks and libraries that enable AI training and inference must run with a smaller footprint (less memory, fewer accelerators), while maintaining accuracy and performance.
- Methods capable of more efficient usage of existing and future computing resources. More sophisticated error recovery and checkpointing is needed in model training and AI workflows.
- Infrastructure that can enable safe and reproducible AI agent implementation and delegation.

Approach: Engage human capital

Researchers seeking to scale up their AI calculations may attempt to do so by repeatedly adding hardware, such as more VRAM memory or additional GPUs or TPUs, to achieve their goals. This is neither tenable nor sustainable, given the current climate of shortages and supply chain challenges, in which power, data center space, and hardware are contested. An alternative approach would improve the underlying software and frameworks that enable these calculations. If focus is given to enhancing the efficiency of the software and frameworks that power existing AI workflows, researchers will more easily run larger calculations and achieve speedups without the need for hardware scaling.

Recent breakthroughs such as TurboQuant may help achieve these ends.⁴⁰ TurboQuant is a compression method that achieves a high reduction in model size, thus enabling faster inference and longer context windows without sacrificing accuracy. Developments like this one increase capacity across multiple sectors. Thus, investments in optimization work, which engages human capital such as AI Engineers and Research Software Engineers (RSEs), make sense across the AI and research landscape. The fruits of this work can deliver enhanced productivity, help with recovery from errors, reduce time to science, solutions, and product, and enable existing hardware and data centers to deliver more value. These gains can be realized from the levels of frontier model training on down to individual model inference and agentic AI. Furthermore, taking a human capital approach to resource usage bottlenecks can leverage programs within NSF, such as NSF Office of Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (OAC) Cybertraining⁴¹ and SCIPe solicitations⁴² that could potentially partner with NAIRR and NSF ACCESS initiatives.^{31,32}

Approach: Collaborate with industry

Collaboration with industry can be a stopgap for obtaining access to AI computing resources for academic work. Partnerships with the major public cloud providers and occasional gifts of the latest GPUs from manufacturers to academic centers help some researchers gain access to advanced computing resources for their AI work.^{36,38,43} However, the heaviest users need not just GPU access, but time on world-class systems with features such as fast interconnect, substantial storage capabilities, ample memory, and many GPUs or Tensor Programming Units (TPUs).³⁵⁻³⁸ To gain access to such systems, these researchers compete with one another for time on overscheduled resources, and their jobs face lengthy waits to run on the most advanced hardware.³⁵ However, renewed, enhanced industry collaborations might help address the shortage of computing hardware access for AI work in academia, by providing spare cycles for academic use or by standing up systems that can be jointly shared between private and public concerns. The current NAIRR pilot program involves industry partners which are contributing capacity and engaging in deep partnerships with academic

researchers. These collaborations between industry and academic research should be taken as successful models for these partnerships, to be continued and further developed.³²

Approach: Prioritize academic work

The most comprehensive models, largest datasets, and most demanding workflows that academics are building outstrip the capabilities of academic AI systems. Thus, a substantial disconnect exists between the work that is presently possible in industry and the work that is presently possible in academia.

This prompts a question: As a society, do we feel that academia should be relegated to pursuing limited work in AI, or do we want to create and support a shared, public ecosystem for substantial academic AI work?³⁵ Such an effort might resemble the supercomputer initiative that NSF undertook with the Teragrid, XSEDE, and then ACCESS programs; it could support burgeoning AI talent and offer substantial AI computing resources for national academic use.³⁷ The question of whether this is desirable must be evaluated by both American society and the taxpayer.

Approach: Document failures

To conserve precious computational resources, and prevent the use of scarce computing time on insoluble problems, some researchers suggest an interesting twist: thoroughly and publicly documenting not only successful research experiments, but also unsuccessful ones.³⁸ Researchers could release technical blogs that include these accounts of failure, including experimental design, data format issues, and other background.⁴⁴ Access to this important information may prevent other researchers from wasting their efforts and expensive computational time pursuing unworkable solutions or repeating failed experiments.

Future directions and questions for discussion

- Academic research often focuses on highly specific or arcane topics that may not be immediately useful or practical in society, whereas industry tends to engage in research in order to create products or other outputs that are immediately useful and scalable to a wider population. How does this translate to the ways that society weighs the importance or usefulness of academic vs. commercial AI work?
- Is there another way for researchers to share AI research best practices outside of the traditional, slow venues of journal publication and existing conferences? What about cross-disciplinary meetings and information sharing germane to AI use in research, or cross-pollination between public and private sphere researchers that use AI? Can these types of cross-disciplinary or public/private exchanges be incentivized?

- Industry collaborations are not a new area for HPC, in which academic HPC centers may offer “memberships” to small companies that need occasional use of research computing infrastructure without incurring ownership and operation expenses. The fees paid help to support the academic HPC center, and the company benefits from HPC access. Renewed industry/academia collaborations might help address the shortage of access to advanced computing infrastructure for AI work, turning the tables by providing academics with spare cycles on commercial systems, or by standing up systems that can be jointly shared between private and public concerns. The NSF NAIRR pilot program has enlisted industry collaborators that include Microsoft, NVIDIA, and Amazon Web Services (AWS); refer to the NAIRR Pilot Portal homepage for the full list of industry collaborators.^{10,45–47} Can this type of collaboration be expanded and deepened? In what other ways can associations between companies and academia enable gains in AI research use, for both parties? Are there new ways that these types of partnerships can be nurtured and enhanced, perhaps at the national level?
- University computing consortia are another common but powerful idea for expanding access to computing resources. When these resources are not in heavy use, access could be given to other universities, on the basis of time zones or other criteria. Could multiple universities collaborate in creating a pool of shared resources for AI work?
- For AI researchers, “brain drain” is real; the biggest opportunities are no longer in academia. At the highest tiers of AI research, researchers are incentivized to leave academia for substantially better salaries and opportunities. They are lured to industry by the opportunity to work on unique problems using the largest computational resources. Academia is then forced to try to compete for these human resources. [37] Ultimately, as a society we must determine whether we value academia’s presence at the scientific frontier for AI work.
- In addition to the access gap to compute resources, some researchers noted a knowledge gap, a “single-sided mirror”, in which industry has access to academic research papers and findings, but academia is unaware of what industry is doing, since important commercial projects are often closed-source and do not publish.³⁸ This creates a knowledge gap for academic researchers who need access to the latest trends. Could information sharing and cross-pollination be encouraged between public and private sphere researchers that use AI?

Challenge: Data management and reproducibility

Managing data for AI work is more onerous than for most traditional HPC workflows, requiring more rigor and more oversight to produce sound, reproducible scientific results. For this reason, data challenges, which include access to datasets, AI-readiness, and data privacy and integrity, can present difficulties for domain scientists using AI techniques in their research. See “Data Wrangling” in Figure 1, which encompasses these tasks.

Data access alone can be a challenge. In some scientific and engineering fields, datasets are closed-source, difficult to acquire, or use proprietary formats, hampering academic work in these areas.^{38,44} This is particularly pronounced in fields that are heavily monetized. In other cases, research datasets are “dark”, published only in obscure journals, or present only on remote servers or storage media. Once datasets are acquired, storage and backup locations, ideally located close to compute, must then be allocated for data that can sometimes occupy many terabytes. The sheer size and complexity of research datasets for AI work can provide an impediment to acquiring or using them. And many times, academic data generation efforts are not fully made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), because of the substantial overhead required for such efforts.^{34,44,48–50}

To help ensure reproducible results, the data used with AI must meet standards of quality, completeness, and freedom from bias. Its provenance and licensing should be well understood, and it should have accompanying metadata and data dictionaries.⁵¹ To achieve this, researchers must first understand the standards they need to enforce. They must prepare their data for use with AI by evaluating, cleansing, and standardizing the needed datasets. They must evaluate raw data, understand its sources, and verify data units and numerical uncertainties.⁴⁹ Data must be well-understood and carefully characterized to be of use in AI workflows; inaccurate and incomplete data is a nagging problem.

While researchers are running AI workloads, they must carefully track the datasets they use to ensure transparency and reproducibility. Monitoring, versioning, tracking data provenance, and documenting training and test data sets throughout introduces additional data management requirements. Though these are common issues for AI-assisted research, the infrastructure and tooling to address these needs are often lacking, leading many researchers to write their own tools and workflows to solve these problems.⁵² The appropriate solution in a given workflow may also depend upon the research problem, dataset size, and the AI type in use, further complicating the application of standard solutions to data problems. Overall, scientists may need to invest considerable research time designing and maintaining workflows to assist with the data management steps for AI workflows.

Another class of data challenge that researchers face concerns data trustworthiness and security, including data integrity and privacy and the handling of sensitive or copyrighted information. These concerns vary in severity by research discipline and data use case, with areas such as medical research and patient data receiving particular focus. Issues in data privacy include patient consent and transparency in data use; data leaks and misuse; and data re-identification risks. For example, the voracious appetite that AI companies have for open data mean that their many scrapers and bots harvest any accessible data indiscriminately to use in their commercial models. If sensitive data or patient information is swept up by these bots, it may become fodder for publicly available Large Language Models (LLMs). This can lead to long-term problems if the data integrated into AI models cannot be extracted, potentially violating commitments made in data management plans, consent forms, or copyright agreements.⁵³ Researchers also cited concerns about data re-identification risks, since AI's ability to connect diverse information can enable it to re-identify previously de-identified health data given surprisingly few details.⁵⁴

Capabilities needed

- Robust metadata schema standards around AI models; containerization; and unified workflow standards to improve AI algorithm portability and reproducibility
- Repositories of high-quality, open-source, well-curated datasets and models adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and metadata standards. Repositories should be integrated with processes that automatically check all data and code submissions against standards, rather than merely requiring submission.
- Highly secure computational spaces (Trusted Compute Environments) to address ethical and regulatory considerations, particularly surrounding data privacy (e.g., HIPAA) and copyrighted information. This includes providing HIPAA-compliant infrastructure and secure preprocessing enclaves for the safe storage, de-identification, and scrubbing of sensitive user data prior to analysis.

Approach: Data availability and sharing

Data availability remains a challenge, and in the most cutting-edge domains and new frontiers, large datasets are not publicly available.^{38,44} However, in some cases, commercial concerns have made their compiled AI-ready datasets available to researchers.³⁴ For example, Meta's FAIR Chemistry group has been releasing large-scale, open access datasets and models for catalysis, materials, and atomic simulations that build on collaborations with academia.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸ Their recently released OMol25 includes simulations of large atomic systems that required 6 billion core hours of compute time, and represent complex interactions between large ensembles of many different elements. Additional partnerships of

this sort between academia and the commercial sphere could bolster the availability of quality data for use by both academic and commercial researchers. The challenge lies in expanding the scope of these public/private collaborations and the disciplines involved in them. Furthermore, securing academic access to commercially lucrative datasets is likely to remain a problem.

Approach: Ensuring metadata and provenance

Clear data provenance and appropriate metadata are essential to establishing trustworthiness, reproducibility, and appropriate use of datasets for AI use. Datasets must include thorough documentation of the underlying measurements, including primary sources, units, and measures of uncertainty, to prevent models from learning noise.⁴⁹ In AI work, datasets must be versionable and clearly marked, to ensure a record of the exact training set used in each run.⁵² Some of the approaches to these issues are technical: using workflows to pool and cross-verify information from databases; cataloging and documenting dataset metadata; automating capture of experimental data, with metadata; and using AI to identify missing or inaccurate information in datasets.^{44,49,52,54} Further, ensuring that researchers are diligent with data readiness is to some degree a training issue; new adopters of AI methods must be properly schooled in appropriate data management and standards for the data for their workloads.

Other potential solutions could introduce new rules and governance: for example, funders could mandate that all data produced with their grants be deposited in a professional, well-curated archive that meets metadata and FAIR standards.⁵⁹ Scientists who develop new datasets could be incentivized to FAIR-ify and publish their datasets to encourage their reuse by others.^{50,52}

Critically, data readiness work varies with the type of AI, the type and size of the dataset, and the project, making it difficult to generalize about or provide a single solution. For example, the question of AI-ready data for electronic structure simulations using synthetic data and that for an international scientific collaboration using petabytes of observation data have vastly different scales and considerations. Regardless, AI-ready data must include understanding data origins, compiling comprehensive metadata, and establishing and maintaining standardized practices.^{44,52} This is work that must be undertaken to ensure good science, and ideally it can be eased by technology and governance together: workflow tools, gateways, rules, and repositories.^{50,60} These critical steps toward AI-ready data must be recognized by funding agencies and other stakeholders; efforts to build data pipelines and instrumentation that automates data collection and eases metadata creation are key parts of AI projects and should be amply supported.^{44,61} The partnership being formed between the

NAIRR pilot and the NSF-funded National Data Platform (NDP) is an example of such an initiative to provide needed capabilities for the future AI ecosystem.^{62,63}

Approach: Data integrity and privacy

Securing sensitive user data away from public-facing APIs, and preventing its storage on ordinary public cloud platforms, is of critical importance. For this reason, availability of HIPAA-compliant server environments in national or cloud infrastructure is crucial to projects in medicine and health informatics.^{43,54} Contractual and legal requirements often necessitate time-consuming preprocessing on user data, such as scrubbing identifying information from data, or simulating user interactions rather than using real-world data directly.^{64,65} While rules and regulations already require it, explicit consent from individuals is paramount when using their data. Researchers must use de-identification techniques, removing names and personal identifiers, before analysis.⁵³

Many of the approaches listed here are already mandated or recommended practice. However, even with such guidelines, diligence is still required from researchers, and compliant behavior is still needed from commercial AI companies that harvest and use open data, since such data can find inroads into unexpectedly insecure datasets. Additional legislation about data privacy may be appropriate to help curtail misuse.

Future directions and questions for discussion

- Data management tasks and pipelines, and the acquisition and verification of data, consume substantial effort and energy for researchers using AI in their work. What if funders better recognized the critical importance of AI-ready datasets by funding efforts to compile and catalogue such datasets for public, academic use? Are there ways to encourage the development of standards for data pipelines or data handling, for different disciplines or use cases?
- What role do education and training in appropriate use of AI have in ensuring appropriate data handling and management, especially for researchers new to AI workloads?
- What role can organizations such as MLCommons play in helping to develop metadata standards, suggest best practices, and provide test datasets?⁶⁶
- Could public/private partnerships be an important part of the future of AI data management guidelines and practice?

Challenge: Democratizing AI access for domain science

The problem of democratizing AI access must be considered; we must ensure that the domain researchers of today are provided with adequate on-ramps to using AI in their work. Further, we need to educate students and future researchers in the use of AI, whether they are bound for the scientific domains or for industry and the wider world. Obstacles to the democratization of AI in academic computing include the discovery and selection of AI-capable compute resources, and steep knowledge gaps for newcomers to AI in research.

Discoverability of compute resources is a substantial challenge for the democratization of AI use in domain research. Researchers seeking to adopt AI methods in their work may not know how or where to access appropriate computing resources.⁶⁵ They may not be aware of the options offered by their own campuses or by the national academic compute resources. They may have trouble determining their eligibility to use the national computing resources or submitting sometimes cumbersome allocation requests. Once available computing resources have been identified, selecting appropriate resources, and acquiring allocations to use them, can be daunting for newcomers to AI use; these researchers often need help evaluating which resources are applicable to their work.^{34,60} Determining the scale of compute needed for a new AI research project, and evaluating and matching data security needs, can be a stumbling block as well. Onboarding, training, allocations, and appropriately selecting and provisioning resources present hurdles to new adopters in AI-assisted research.

Another democratization challenge lies in the knowledge gaps experienced by new adopters of AI techniques in research.^{53,60} Interacting with cutting-edge AI requires specialized knowledge of the typical systems and workflows, often creating a high barrier to entry for non-computer scientists.³⁴ To be effective in their AI work, researchers must learn about AI software and techniques and the data handling and workflows needed to run these types of computations. Setting up the necessary computing environments, handling complex models, managing datasets, and performing distributed training can incur substantial overhead for the uninitiated.

Capabilities needed

- AI Cyberinfrastructure Facilitators providing human capital and capacity to help domain scientists translate and map science problems to AI methods and resources.
- AI tools and assistants aimed at aiding researchers in applying AI techniques and appropriately using resources.

- AI and domain science environments (Science Gateways and portals) that bring together data, software, models, tools, workflows, and computing resources in an approachable way for domain science communities.
- Repositories of AI use cases and example workflows that provide educational resources and documented protocols.

Approach: AI Facilitators

One researcher recommended establishing “AI Facilitators”, experts tasked with keeping abreast of rapidly changing AI technologies and supporting the community in their use. These experts would be trained to guide domain scientists in choosing and implementing appropriate computational tools and methods.⁵⁷ Such facilitators could be attached to, and specialize in, support of specific national or campus resources, similar to the XSEDE/ACCESS “Campus Champion” model and the NAIRR SCPE CI professional, or in concert with university libraries. Educational efforts should focus on teaching AI concepts to experimentalists, and on teaching computational experts how to work effectively with complex, real-world data sets for AI. Both Research Software Engineers and AI Engineers can be effective in these roles for aiding domain scientists in adopting and applying AI.

Approach: Discoverability and accessibility of computing resources

To help new adopters, researchers recommended improving the discoverability of computing resources, as well as the available documentation about their features and use. One obstacle to access may simply be the lack of knowledge that these tools and platforms are available, and where to find them. One researcher commented that more organized and thorough documentation, and light “advertising” of existing opportunities and resources, such as might be provided by webinars, hands-on training, and workshops, can help.⁶⁵

Researchers added that a streamlined process for applying for computing resource allocations would aid prospective AI users who set out to use the public, national computing resources.^{34,67} Furthermore, on-demand access, or speedier turnarounds for resource access, would be a great benefit to new adopters.

Thoroughly trained, specialized chatbots can be a useful assist to users new to a resource or process. Chatbots can retrieve system-specific information from documentation, then serve as virtual guides, coaching users as they apply for allocations and determine how to access computing resources for their AI work.^{34,44,68} Open source LLM platforms such as Illinois Chat can be trained on detailed technical documents, notes, and system specs, and deployed by resource providers to provide

advanced chatbot functionality so that users can orient themselves on the systems.⁹ Judicious deployment of specialized chatbots may also cut down on the time that resource providers must spend providing user support.

Approach: Science Gateways

Interviewees emphasized the importance of making models and datasets accessible to researchers through science gateways that provide clearinghouses for models and AI-ready data sets. Using these platforms, researchers new to AI techniques can engage with exemplars and learn how to use the methods in their own work.³⁴ In earlier sections, we discussed the issues of data management and matching data to models. Providing gateways can help smooth out the learning curve and help new adopters. For example, the Garden project's science gateway containerizes models, promoting discoverability and reuse by associating models with the appropriate data, computing resources, and metadata.⁷ Under continuing development now is the National Research Platform (NRP), an academic science gateway that connects researchers and educators to AI and HPC resources, data storage, and networking.⁶⁹ Similarly, the evolving NAIRR Pilot Portal supports computational, data, and training resources to advance AI-informed research.¹⁰ Sustained support of these and similar platforms and gateways will ease the way for researchers new to AI methods by providing them with examples and best practices for adoption in their research.

Supporting new AI research users by extending AI-focused gateways such as Garden, NRP, and NAIRR Pilot Portal, as well as Foundry ML, Diamond.io, and others^{6,8}, is essential to the democratization of AI in research. Even commercial AI platforms, and collaborations with industry in the form of platforms such as HuggingFace and Modal, help deliver access to models, compute cycles, and data for learning and simple applications.¹¹⁻¹³ One researcher envisioned a "virtuous cycle" that would connect data sources, model training, and model publication and reuse using such platforms and utilities, enabling researchers and students to learn the ropes and begin to use these technologies in their research.³⁴

Approach: Targeted use case and examples

As one researcher stated, "the transition from being merely competent with AI tools to using them effectively is a significant challenge."⁵² Adopting AI methods for research incurs the overhead of new requirements that span computing resources, software, workflows, data management, and more. Therefore, training new adopters of these technologies will involve a variety of tools and techniques. Concrete use cases and examples, as well as tutorials and guides that take an approach similar to Software Carpentry, are essential to demonstrate the AI capabilities of platforms and gateways.^{68,70} Researchers must learn what AI tools are available, what kinds of problems they are appropriate for,

and what AI tools already exist and need not be re-developed.⁵² Existing tools can be built into the AI-focused science gateways described above to provide comprehensive learning platforms. Workshops held by resource providers can help new adopters take resources and software through its paces and provide them with examples and best practices that they can bring into their own work. As discussed above, open source chatbots such as Illinois Chat can also be used to retrieve information from documentation and tutorial materials, and serve as virtual tutors or teaching assistants, coaching users as they learn to use these technologies.⁹

Aiding new users on AI resources can boost both research and education; as a society we must engage in training new AI researchers, experts, users, and the future workforce. Training, education, and workforce development for AI use go hand in hand with democratization.

Future directions and questions for discussion

- It's important to note that innovations can be contributed even by those who are new to using AI. One researcher described a student hackathon that surfaced new ideas for hypothesis generation, research data management (conversing with databases), scientific communication, and building natural language interfaces for complex software.³⁴ Working together with seasoned researchers, new adopters of this technology may be able to provide insights that are useful for the discipline.
- An underlying concern for democratization may be the sparsity of sustainability plans for academic AI platforms. Many platforms developed in academia, AI-related and otherwise, rely on grant funding and are offered for use by all users—researchers, students, and the public—for free. Is there a way for even academic AI platforms to monetize and thus become more self-sustaining? Or, does this contrast too much with the standard practices of typical academic platforms? Do these concerns intersect with those discussed in the Sustainability Blueprint Factory?²

Challenge: Fostering responsible use of AI in research

Democratizing AI access in research must be balanced with fostering judicious, intentional, and ethically responsible use of these powerful techniques. Though work in many scientific domains does not touch on hot button ethical issues such as sensitive personal information or intellectual property, the question of responsible AI use is still fundamentally relevant. Regardless of their scientific domain, researchers must have an understanding of the AI techniques they are using, choose appropriate models for research problems, and consider the future availability of their datasets and the reproducibility of their computational results. The combination of these considerations forms the foundation of reproducible, defensible science using AI methods.

A complicating factor for this discussion is the fact that AI is a moving target. AI is evolving so rapidly that staying abreast of methods and best practices is an onerous task. Many effective research systems dovetail different types of smaller AI systems with other codes and workflows, so each subsystem must be evaluated, tested, and considered separately. Furthermore, the types of computations used, scale of datasets, and other considerations mean that recommendations for responsible use must be somewhat general.

Responsible AI use starts with proper technical operation of AI models, used with appropriate data. Issues related to data readiness were discussed at length above, in the *Data management and reproducibility* section, but are again relevant here. Researchers must ensure that their models and data accurately represent target problems and are examined for bias. This process can be nuanced, since sometimes, data imbalance can lead to the appearance of algorithmic bias.⁵⁴ Furthermore, models and algorithms must be used appropriately on systems and problems for which they are intended, and should not be generalized to new contexts without careful scrutiny. Researchers must take care to understand and clearly document the details of the models and data they use and the assumptions they make in their research.⁶⁵

Ensuring the explainability of results is especially important when AI is involved in scientific research. In science, researchers typically seek to understand how things work, produce scholarship that can be clearly explained, and generate reproducible experimental results. Unfortunately, the lack of interpretability of “black box” algorithms can run counter to these scientific goals.^{38,52,71,72} These models have their uses in science, but understanding the link between input and output and establishing trustworthiness can be complicated.⁵⁹ Furthermore, AI has the potential to produce conclusions that are not reproducible or that do not follow from the provided data.^{53,65} Overall,

the ability to explain how models arrive at their results is important for establishing reproducibility, building trust, and encouraging adoption of AI-based systems. The challenge lies in incorporating these guidelines in the research setting, producing trustworthy results worthy of the label “science”.

In fields such as medicine, the potential impact from errors in an AI system can be substantial. As one researcher pointed out, the impact of an error in a system used to provide diagnoses for many patients is much greater than that from a clinician making one mistake with a single patient’s case.⁷³ Researchers working in areas such as disease prediction must also consider the potential for a prediction itself to cause harm. For example, a prediction of high disease risk may itself cause considerable stress to a patient.⁵⁴ While the proper technical use of AI is clearly an essential consideration in the development of large scale predictive medical systems, other questions unrelated to such technical issues must also be weighed in order to serve the human patient.

Researchers new to AI use may be tempted to adopt these techniques uncritically, lacking a nuanced understanding of how the AI tools work, the problems on which they are appropriate, the data they rely on, or their limitations.⁵³ Rushing to adopt AI in an inappropriate context, without critical thinking, can result in incorrect conclusions, shoddy science, and wasted compute cycles. In part, this problem stems from AI knowledge gaps in the workforce, even in research domains. One researcher noted that traditional CI or domain science experts often lack expertise in training or fine-tuning AI models.⁶⁰ And, since AI technology is changing rapidly, identifying the relevant technology and correctly applying it to the problem at hand can present a real challenge, even for those with some facility in AI.

Another broader avenue for concern relates to the effect of AI-driven research on human society, employment, and the environment. The power consumption and environmental impact of large models and compute infrastructure, as well as the carbon footprint of manufacturing new computer hardware compared to the reuse of older, existing hardware, were mentioned by interviewees.^{35,49,53,74} Some researchers also noted that using AI in research risks exacerbating inequality and the global digital divide. Namely, access to powerful AI models and computing resources is limited in the Global South, making it difficult for researchers there to achieve results comparable to those in the Global North.^{43,64,74} Furthermore, the human tendency to gravitate toward elaborate solutions may steer funders and others toward complex AI powered systems to address problems that may respond well to more elementary solutions.⁵³ Researchers also rightly raised concerns that the spread of AI in the workplace might affect even highly skilled research jobs.^{35,53} They pointed out the need for workforce retraining to enable people to master the skills and use AI ethically, legally, and efficiently, to address and counter this risk.

Capabilities needed

- Dedicated testbeds that are instrumented with sufficient guardrails for safe prototyping and validation of frontier-level AI model development as well as AI workflows.
- Infrastructure that provides a streamlined, transparent process for computing resource allocations.
- Tools for monitoring AI workflows
- Tools for enhancing scientific workflows and incorporating improved composition, monitoring, and resource mapping.
- Platforms and AI frameworks that enable additional human feedback and control within AI and data processing workflows.
- Power-efficient implementations of data processing pipelines along with AI software optimization methods.

Approach: Guidelines and tools for reusability

Researchers discussed the importance of tools and guidelines for making models testable, transparent, explainable, and reusable. Though challenges arise from the black box nature of deep learning models, better metadata, runtimes, and cyberinfrastructure can help support these goals for many methods. One researcher noted that conferences and journals require code repositories but fail to check for reproducibility, and recommended making these requirements more stringent to serve the research community's need for reusable models.⁷⁵ This notion was echoed by another interviewee, who cited a study that surveyed 75 AI software packages in several different categories, and found that only 25% of these could be easily reused, highlighting a substantial gap between published AI research and its practical reusability.⁷⁶ Explicitly addressing the portability of AI algorithms requires metadata to describe the relevant data, software, and runtime environments.⁷⁷ A combination of containerization, workflow standards, registries, metadata schemas, and provenance capture may be necessary to address this comprehensively.⁵⁰

In order to promote AI transparency, reproducibility, and reuse in research, researchers emphasize the continued development of tools to assist with AI use. For example, existing scientific workflow tools are being enhanced to incorporate AI technologies for improved workflow composition, monitoring, and resource mapping.⁶⁰ Their use will assist researchers in handling complex computational tasks for AI workloads, and improving transparency. Researchers also recommend an increased focus on the development of essential tools for AI workflow profiling and dedicated testbeds for AI prototype development. There is a need for more such tools to support the development, validation, testing, and explainability of AI workflows.³⁵ The continual evolution of AI suggests that development of CI

to provide these tools in different research settings, regimes, and AI types is an important goal for funders and other research stakeholders to pursue.

Approach: Interdisciplinary teams

Several interviewees stressed how interdisciplinary project teams can promote ethical and appropriate AI use in a research setting.^{43,54} In some large research projects, teams may encompass domain scientists, engineers, computer scientists, and others in order to build instruments, collect data, build and run computational environments and workflows, train and run models, and interpret results.³⁷ Each individual researcher operates within their area of expertise and can help guide sensible decisions using their background and strengths. Such teams with diverse skill sets, from domain experts to computer science and CI experts, can more easily discuss and address ethical concerns from the design phase through processing and analysis. Projects that take such a multidisciplinary approach can better identify ethical issues and other pitfalls that might be overlooked by researchers from a single background.⁴³

Approach: Education and training

To combat the misapplication of AI techniques, education in current AI methods and techniques is necessary for both students and seasoned researchers who are taking strides into AI use in their work. While education has been discussed in the subsection “Approach: Targeted use cases and examples”, it bears repeating here. A range of approaches to new and continuing education in AI, including appropriate training, tutorials and examples, guidance and mentoring, and program or governmental requirements can help ensure that new adopters start their research off right and use AI techniques responsibly, regardless of their starting point. Numerous domain scientists we interviewed are prioritizing teaching AI techniques and responsible AI use to their university students. They contend that the tools and methods of AI must be used, understood, and mastered by the future research workforce.^{44,59} Training and workforce education efforts can also help address concerns about job loss due to AI incursions into the research workplace; those who can ably use AI in their work will be better able to adapt to a changing research landscape.

Approach: Human in the loop

Numerous participants highlighted the need for researchers to perform critical evaluation of AI outputs, validate results against expectations, and keep the human scientist tightly integrated into the process of using AI in research.^{44,72} For example, using AI technologies can make code development itself faster, but shifts the burden to validation and verification, in part because concerns about the trustworthiness and reproducibility of results are heightened when code writing is assisted by

machines.⁶⁰ The diversity of AI approaches to research problems make it difficult to generalize; to evaluate their trustworthiness, outputs from AI use can be evaluated statistically, or against results from non-AI techniques. However, simple accuracy metrics can be insufficient, especially in health care, where false negatives and false positives must be considered as well.⁵⁴ Regardless, output validation, and keeping the human researcher in the loop to validate output is important across disciplines.^{44,72} Researchers suggest adoption of standards and computational tools to assist with these processes, such as testbed environments instrumented with sufficient guardrails to help detect unusual behavior.⁶⁰ Because of variation in disciplines, datasets, and techniques, a variety of approaches may be needed. However, human oversight and critical assessment of the results from AI work is necessary, as is building verification and validation into these systems.^{44,72}

Approach: Optimize for efficiency

Optimization for AI-based work is a vitally important part of responsible use, since environmental impact can be mitigated by lessening power consumption. One need only consider the splash made by DeepSeek's efficiency gains when it was first introduced.¹⁹ If a large, complex LLM can show such efficiency gains, surely strides can be made for other, simpler types of AI as well. However, optimization is easily neglected when researchers are struggling to get their research pipelines up and running. A renewed focus on research processes, tools, and efforts toward optimization could result in a drastic reduction in AI's energy use.⁶¹ A drive for efficiency gains could be brought to bear on different areas of AI research pipelines, from data management to hardware to testing and validation. For example, efficiency improvements in dataset processing automation would have a substantial impact on the energy use of experiments that handle and label tens of terabytes of data.⁶¹ Furthermore, small efficiency gains in transformer architecture would drastically reduce energy use for AI pipelines. Efforts that emphasize optimization for AI processes and architectures would help address concerns of environmental impact and responsible use of AI, and should be prioritized and encouraged by funders and in research programs.

Future directions and questions for discussion

- Several researchers who are using AI techniques in their work mentioned the problem of skepticism; in some scientific disciplines, funders are reluctant to back explicitly AI-related research projects.^{61,78} Researchers described the strategies they use to outline computational work that employs AI techniques, minimizing the emphasis on AI in order not to alarm their funders. Other researchers mention skepticism among the medical community about the use of AI diagnostic or forecasting tools in a clinical setting.^{54,67} What can be done to increase the comfort of funders or adopters? How can their specific concerns be addressed and assuaged?

- Another question raised concerned appropriate use of AI where it conflicts with stated policy. Some solicitations and conferences still specify that AI may not be used in materials preparation; some universities discourage the use of AI in research. However, AI productivity tools can be useful to streamline, clarify, and copyedit academic writing. Is using AI tools for such tasks a violation of policy in these cases?

Recommendations

Academic researchers today are using AI for an astounding range of tasks, ranging from computational to technical, and even creative. They are optimizing existing calculations and processes; designing new scientific equipment; forecasting disease states, and performing other scientific and computational feats that would have seemed impossible in the recent past. The research they pursue is often focused on using AI to optimize scientific calculations and processes; to discover new techniques, materials, and sensors; and to study, safeguard, and improve AI use in research. These awesome tools provide computational horsepower that makes an excellent complement to human scientific creativity and innovation. Used well, they can remove some of the most repetitious and onerous tasks from academic research, allowing scientists to more easily attain research goals. This research hinges upon the availability of appropriate computing resources and the datasets, software, techniques, and know-how that enables safe, reproducible, transparent experimentation, learning, and innovation.

In order to better support domain researchers in their adoption of AI for research goals, we must keep several important considerations in mind. Support for researchers takes a number of forms, just as researchers across the disciplines have different support needs. One of the foremost is education and continued guidance for new and learning AI adopters; another is access to advanced computing resources so that researchers can operate without resource constraints.

In order to support domain research using AI, we recommend the following considerations:

RECOGNIZE THE ROLE OF RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERS IN BUILDING THE AI RESEARCH ECOSYSTEM

The effective and trustworthy utilization of AI in scientific research necessitates the creation of sophisticated computational tooling and cyberinfrastructure (CI) that extends beyond traditional High-Performance Computing (HPC) workflows. We must incentivize the ongoing development of tools for core AI components, and provide functionality including automated data capture, data pooling, and workflow profiling, to ensure research AI can achieve its full potential. Furthermore, much of the scalability, usability, and reproducibility of AI research depends on the people who are building workflows, interfaces, and operational infrastructure. This places a substantial emphasis on the capacity of AI Engineers, Research Software Engineers, and other CI professionals to develop, deploy, maintain, train, and support these new and emerging CI resources for AI. Therefore, efforts to create and sustain human capital and capacity in these roles are crucial for building and supporting the AI ecosystem needed to drive cutting-edge AI research and application.

ENCOURAGE DEVELOPMENT OF DATA PIPELINES, TOOLS, AND TECHNIQUES FOR AI RESEARCH

By its nature, AI used for scientific research requires computational tooling to ensure reproducibility and trustworthiness. Data management and preparation techniques, workflows and processes for training, and verification and validation for AI require different and more elaborate software tooling than do the comparable HPC workflows more familiar to scientific researchers. AI-informed research is still playing catch-up to traditional HPC workflows in the sciences; more investments in tooling and infrastructure are needed. Additionally, a focus on optimizing AI processes and data handling can ensure sensible resource consumption while these technologies are developed to their fullest. This includes developing workflows to pool and cross-verify data; automate data capture; and identify missing or inaccurate elements of datasets, as well as tools for profiling AI workflows and testbeds for AI prototype development. We must incentivize the development and continual improvement of tools for these vital components of AI processing so that science can use the full potential of AI. This means bringing focus on these development activities across the levels of funders, institutions, disciplines, and all the way down to individual research groups. Prioritizing AI tool and pipeline development will enable research AI to thrive.

STRENGTHEN STANDARDS AND GUIDELINES FOR APPROPRIATE AI USE IN RESEARCH

As the use of AI in research proliferates, reproducibility and reusability for these techniques must retain focus. To assist with this, both publications and funders should implement stricter standards for data and code repositories that also ensure reproducibility, to satisfy the research community's appetite for reusable models. Encouraging rigorous recordkeeping in research AI, including data provenance and metadata, must accompany the availability of tools to meet these ends. Clear metadata should accompany publications and proposals, describing the data, software, and runtime environments used by AI-assisted research. The repositories containing results should be made publicly available so that others can build on the results of this research.

SUPPORT AND GROW SCIENCE GATEWAYS FOR AI

Teaching and learning for AI techniques in science is a moving target; this fact is unlikely to change anytime soon. To ensure responsible AI use in research now and workforce development for the future, learners need adequate support. New adopters of AI technologies must be provided with training, examples, and straightforward access to software, hardware, and techniques that meet researchers, their students, and their computing skills where they are.

To address this objective, we must build, enhance, and sustain science gateways that provide learning environments, as well as tutorials and guides; computing resource documentation; and working examples. Furthermore, these materials must keep pace with current practice, offering cutting-edge examples, computing resource access, and new techniques so that learners can stay abreast of developments. The ongoing support of these platforms, and the continual development of materials showcasing new techniques, is crucial. Once again, encouraging the continued development of these teaching and learning resources will be the responsibility of both funders and institutions.

EXPAND TEACHING OF AI

Science gateways and learning resources are not the whole story for teaching AI. In order to foster workforce development as well as responsible use of AI, coursework at all levels must be offered. Institutions nationwide should develop coursework that teaches AI to audiences ranging from undergraduates to seasoned researchers. Formal coursework, tutorials, workshops, hackathons, and other means of teaching can be employed to train, retrain, and continue to engage learners in the use of AI for research.

FORGE PARTNERSHIPS BETWEEN INDUSTRY AND ACADEMIA

Partnerships across academia and industry must be renewed and strengthened to create new datasets, resources, software, workflows, and solutions for AI. Without the critical workforce development that takes place in academia, industry will be deprived of the experts it needs to develop and operate the next generation of AI systems. Additionally, academic institutions that may be more accustomed to competing than collaborating must join forces to build and host scarce hardware and CI and develop software and techniques for AI. It is imperative that researchers across academia and industry work together to promote computing resource availability and access, to develop new datasets and software, and to make gains in AI together, as a society.

IDENTIFY INDICATORS OF SUCCESS

As the AI ecosystem for domain research evolves over the next decade, the academic community should identify metrics to measure maturity and success for the uptake, adoption, and use of these technologies in research. Examples of such indicators could include time-to-first-use for new AI users; adoption by institutions without strong local AI infrastructure; the number of reusable AI workflows and exemplars; an increase in the number of AI Engineers and Research Software Engineers (RSEs) who are actively supporting scientific AI research; and growth in researchers and students trained in and using AI for their research. An effort by the AI research community to periodically review these indicators will provide feedback on areas of the ecosystem that need focus or refinement, and help guide ongoing decisions.

Summary

This report summarizes results and conclusions from the 30 researcher interviews conducted for SGX3's AI Blueprint Factory. Researchers were chosen for their active use of AI and their variety of academic disciplines, seniorities, institution types, and US geographic regions. The overarching purpose of the AI Blueprint Factory is to understand the needs of research communities that use AI techniques on national-scale computing infrastructure. In this report we outline how researchers use AI in their work, and identify common challenges, concerns, and pain points. With these conclusions we forecast the features and resources needed to support AI-enabled research in the near future. SGX3 intends this work to inform future access to hardware and software, training, functionality, and features to support AI-driven academic research.

Appendices

Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BoF	Birds of a Feather
CI	Cyberinfrastructure
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DOE	United States Department of Energy
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IRB	Institutional Review Board
LLM	Large Language Model
NAIRR	NSF National AI Research Resource
NRP	NSF National Research Platform
NSF	United States National Science Foundation
OAC	NSF Office of Advanced Computing
RSE	Research Software Engineer
SCIFE	NSF Strengthening the Cyberinfrastructure Professionals Ecosystem
SGCI	NSF Science Gateways Community Institute
SGX3	NSF Science Gateways Center of Excellence
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
VRAM	Video Random Access Memory

AI Blueprint Factory core team members

The core team recruited to guide the AI Blueprint Factory consisted of 8 research computing and domain science experts. This group devised the interview guide used for the study, recruited domain science and cyberinfrastructure experts for interviews, and conducted the interviews.

The AI Blueprint Factory core team members are:

- Chi-kwan Chan, Steward Observatory and Department of Astronomy, University of Arizona
- Amy Connolly, Department of Physics, The Ohio State University
- Ewa Deelman, Information Sciences Institute, University of Southern California

- Christian Garcia, Texas Advanced Computing Center, University of Texas, Austin
- Rob Quick, Research Computing Infrastructure, University of Kentucky
- Joe Stubbs, Texas Advanced Computing Center, University of Texas, Austin
- Jeanette Sperhac, San Diego Supercomputer Center, University of California San Diego
- Huanmei Wu, Barnett College of Public Health, Temple University

Recruitment letter

The following recruitment letter was approved for use in the recruitment of AI Blueprint Factory subjects by core team members' institutional IRBs. It was emailed to a wide range of contacts.

Dear *Recipient's Name*,

I represent the NSF Science Gateways Center of Excellence (SGX3) at San Diego Supercomputer Center. We are pleased to invite you to participate in a research study being conducted by University of California San Diego, focused on artificial intelligence (AI) use and future needs in scientific research. Our goal is to study cyberinfrastructure capabilities required to support researchers who are using AI in their work.

We are seeking participants who meet the following criteria:

- graduate student, postdoc, faculty, or staff researcher
- engaged in research that utilizes AI methods or techniques
- creates, provides, or uses tools, software, datasets, or cyberinfrastructure for AI-enabled research

Your participation will consist of an online Zoom interview lasting approximately one hour. The study is being conducted online under the auspices of San Diego Supercomputer Center, University of California San Diego, 9836 Hopkins Drive, La Jolla, California, 92093. If you meet the above criteria and are interested in participating, please contact Jeanette Sperhac at jsperhac@ucsd.edu.

We appreciate your consideration of this important study. Your participation could make a significant contribution to advancing cyberinfrastructure for AI-enabled research.

Exempt study information sheet

The following information sheet was approved for use with AI Blueprint Factory subjects by core team members' institutional IRBs.

You are being invited to participate in a research study titled "AI Blueprint Factory". This study is being conducted by Jeanette Sperhac from University of California San Diego, representing the NSF-funded Science Gateways Center of Excellence (SGX3). You were selected to participate in this study because of your current and ongoing work with Artificial Intelligence (AI) in your research.

The purpose of this research study is to better understand the AI needs of research communities that use national-scale computing infrastructure. Your participation in this research should last approximately 1 (one) hour. If you agree to take part in this study, you will be asked to answer questions about your experience and use of AI in your research. The session will be held remotely using Zoom. Your responses will be captured in written notes and in a recording of the session. The recording will be used only to transcribe the session. At any time during the interview, you may ask for the recording to be halted.

Your participation in this study is completely voluntary and you can withdraw at any time. Choosing not to participate or withdrawing will result in no penalty to you. You are free to skip any question that you choose.

If you have questions about this project or if you have a related problem, you may contact the researcher, Jeanette Sperhac, jsperhac@ucsd.edu. If you have any questions concerning your rights as a research subject, you may contact the University of California San Diego Office of IRB Administration at irb@ucsd.edu.

By participating in this research, you are indicating that you are at least 18 years old, have read this consent form, and agree to participate in this research study. Please keep this consent form for your records.

Interview guide

The following interview guide was developed by the AI Blueprint Factory core team, and was used to guide all discussions with interviewees.

BASIC INFORMATION

- What is your name?
- What is your discipline, field of study, subfield?
- What is your educational level/history?
- What is your current institution and departmental affiliation (list several if appropriate)?
- What is your current role there (list several if appropriate)?
- What project are you currently working on?
 - ◊ Tell me about your field of research.
 - ◊ Tell me about your research workflow.
 - ◊ What sort of data does it involve?
 - ◊ What analytical tools do you use?
 - ◊ What computing resources do you use?

AI USE IN RESEARCH

- Are you currently using AI at any point in your research?
- What type or types of AI are you working with? (predictive, generative, etc.)
- At what points in your research are you actively using AI, and how?
- How do you characterize your involvement with AI in your research—are you primarily active in data, algorithm development, or cyberinfrastructure? Alternately, are you active in more than one of these areas? If multiple areas, what are the rough percentages?
- Please describe your experience/history using AI.
- How long have you been using AI?
- Do you have experience with other types of AI?
- Did you study AI formally? If so, please describe the program or course.

GOALS FOR USING AI

- What is your objective or goal with AI in your research?
- Are you able to attain that goal using AI?
- How did you achieve these goals before you used AI?
- Would it have been possible? How would it be different?
- What resources would have been required to do so?

- What types of AI do you hope to use in future research? How would you use them? What is preventing you from using those now?

INTERACTING WITH AI

- Are you using specific computing resources for the AI work (national lab or NSF, university, private or corporate cloud, other)? If so, which ones?
- How do you leverage data resources for your AI usage? Are these external to the other resources you use?
- What sort of interface are you using to interact with AI (e.g. command line, notebooks, APIs, other)? If using multiple interfaces, what are the rough percentages?
- Does your work involve data provenance and/or data management concerns? If so, what type of infrastructure are you using to address this?
- What improvements would you hope to see in reproducibility and collaboration of data?
- Are you using workflow tools to execute machine learning pipelines, and if so, which one? Was customization or programming necessary to set up the pipeline? Did you perform the customization or did a team member or other do so?
- How would you describe the ease or difficulty of working with AI in this case?
- Are there pieces of your workflow that were cumbersome, or that you had to invent yourself?
- What were the gaps in what was available to you for your AI-based research?
- What kinds of features, tooling, or support would make this sort of research easier?
- Are you using any science gateways for this or other work? If so:
 - ◊ Which gateway or gateways are you using?
 - ◊ Please describe the work and how the gateway supports it.
 - ◊ Do gateways provide the resources that you need for AI work?
 - ◊ If not, what are your reasons for not using gateways?
 - ◊ Are there resources or features needed for such work that gateways lack now?

ETHICS, CONCERNS, AND FUTURE

- Do you have any ethical concerns about using AI in your research?
- Do you intend to undertake other AI-based projects in the future? Why or why not?
- What are your largest concerns with regard to your AI use? This might include the expense, ethical questions, complexity of use, availability of resources, or other concerns.

Focus group guide

The focus group session held at PEARC'23 followed the Brain Trust format.^{22,23} Participants in the session were divided into four groups of equal size, with each group selecting one of the four questions posed by the facilitator. The session procedure is as follows:

POSING THE QUESTION (5 MINS)

(1 min) The facilitator poses the questions and prepares the groups to think creatively.

(4 mins) The groups may ask follow-up questions and raise issues with the entire group.

RAPID FIRE WRITING (5 MINS)

Using one Post-it sticky note per idea, group members write down as many ideas as possible.

The guidelines:

- One idea per Post-it
- Do not pause to refine
- Do not eliminate any ideas

CONSOLIDATING AND CLASSIFYING (10 MINS)

Participants consolidate and classify their ideas, removing duplicates and determining which category is appropriate for each idea. The category choices are:

- Easy, just do it
- Highest impact
- Wild and crazy
- Important but requires investment

GROUP PRESENTATIONS (20 MINS)

Participants place all sticky notes on a pre-designed grid, according to their classifications.

Each team appoints one member as spokesperson. This member places the group's sticky notes in the categories and briefly explains the reasoning. Group discussion follows, and all participant notes and their categorizations are captured for later analysis.

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